

DIGITAL GAMES WHICH HAS SENSIBLE INFLUENCE ON IMPROVING PERSONAL VOCABULARY

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Introduction.

Extramural English (EE) activities, which include learner-initiated activities outside the classroom such as playing digital games, have been shown to positively impact vocabulary size and English language proficiency (Sundqvist, 2009; Sundqvist & Sylvén, 2012). This study examines the gaming habits, experiences, and perceptions of Pakistani high school students regarding incidental English vocabulary acquisition through online multiplayer video games. Data was collected through an online questionnaire and semi-structured interviews. Of the 88 students who responded to the survey, 23 volunteered for interviews, and five were selected based on their survey responses. The survey data was quantitatively analyzed, and thematic narrative analysis was applied to the interview data. The findings indicate a consensus on the beneficial role of video games in incidental vocabulary acquisition, attributed to the low-pressure context, heightened attention and engagement, and the shift from incidental learning to self-directed learning.

With widespread internet access and the prevalence of English media on mobile devices, informal language acquisition has become more common. Electronic devices offer numerous opportunities for informal English learning, including through video games.

This study contributes to understanding how video games can enhance second language vocabulary acquisition, focusing specifically on online multiplayer role-playing games (MMORPGs). These games, such as World of Warcraft, Second Life, and PUBG, involve interaction among players from diverse backgrounds, necessitating the use of English. Gamers often engage in MMORPGs for enjoyable social interactions and may not consciously recognize the language learning benefits. However, their language skills can be influenced by various linguistic elements within the games, such as game orientation, storylines, and communication with other players.

Previous research has shown that video games can positively affect language learning. For instance, some studies found that games improve learner affect and vocabulary retention (Hitosugi, Schmidt, & Hayashi, 2014) and support long-term retention of target language vocabulary (Franciosi et al., 2016). A study on MMORPGs found that incidental vocabulary acquisition can occur rapidly due to frequent word exposure and visual representations within the game (Maier, 2016). However, most research focuses on general language learning rather than specific vocabulary acquisition (Saragi et al., 1978; Schrader & McCreery, 2008; Steinkuehler, 2010; Bischoff & Gilliland, 2015), and few studies examine informal language

learning contexts like those explored here. This study aims to fill this gap by examining Egyptian students' perceptions of vocabulary acquisition through MMORPGs using an online survey and informal interviews.

The questionnaire aimed to explore students' gaming habits and their relationship with vocabulary proficiency. By comparing time spent gaming with vocabulary test performance, the study found that students who played English games for 30 to 40 hours a week made fewer mistakes. Surprisingly, students who played 10 hours or less per week achieved the highest scores, while those playing 10-20 hours had slightly lower accuracy. The discrepancy may be due to a higher error rate among students with more gaming hours or the possibility that more frequent players might make more mistakes due to hurried responses. Most existing research on L2 learning has addressed language acquisition more broadly, with only a few studies focusing specifically on vocabulary acquisition (Saragi, Nation, & Meister, 1978; Schrader & McCreery, 2008; Steinkuehler, 2010; Bischoff & Gilliland, 2015). Additionally, much of this research has been conducted within formal L2 educational programs, where the learning environment is structured rather than incidental (Zheng, Bischoff, & Gilliland, 2015). In contrast, this study investigates incidental vocabulary acquisition in a non-academic setting. Furthermore, there has been limited research on user attitudes and experiences in the Egyptian context. This study focuses on extramural English and its impact on students' English proficiency, particularly examining the link between gaming and vocabulary acquisition. By building on previous research from different contexts, this study provides an overview of informal English vocabulary learning in Egypt. It aims to explore Egyptian gamers' perceptions of second language learning and vocabulary acquisition in MMORPGs through an online survey and informal interviews.

The questionnaire sought to assess both students' gaming habits and their vocabulary proficiency. It explored the relationship between the time spent gaming and vocabulary test performance by comparing the number of correct answers to the amount of time spent playing English games.

Results indicate that students who played English games for 30 to 40 hours a week made fewer mistakes. Interestingly, students who played for 10 hours or less achieved the highest scores, while those playing 10-20 hours had slightly lower accuracy. This suggests that students playing 10 hours or fewer per week performed better, with these students scoring 100% on all 10 tested words. In comparison, those playing 10-20 hours had 9 words with 100% accuracy. A potential reason for this could be that only 24.5% of students played 10 hours or fewer a week, whereas 52.5% played for 10-20 hours. The higher number of students in the 10-20 hour range might have led to more typos and mistakes, possibly due to hurried responses. Although the study's findings are not definitive due to the small sample size, a trend suggests that increased gaming correlates with better vocabulary understanding.

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